

EXCERPT OF INTERVIEW SCRIPT

Thank you for participating in our survey about the use of chatrooms by developers! Do we have your permission to record the content of this interview for future use? Based on your survey answers, you are a {Slack/Gitter} user and you identify as a {maintainer/contributor/user} of the project associated to the chatroom. I will ask you a series of questions with the goal of clarifying your survey answers, and possibly validating or rejecting other possible answers. Please feel free to go off on any tangents that you judge relevant to the topic.

(Part 1)

Can you tell us about your motivations for contributing to the chatrooms when asking questions?

Prompts:

Response time?

Quality of the help?

The community of developers?

Can you tell us about your motivations for contributing to the chatrooms when answering questions?

Prompts:

Community building?

Personal gain?

Personal enjoyment?

(Part 2)

Do you believe that {Slack/Gitter} has a noticeable impact on the associated projects in terms of the quality of the code produced, the issue resolution, the productivity of the developers?

Prompts:

Support project awareness?

Prioritization/Visibility of issues and features?

User support?

Improved productivity?

(Part 3)

What are the most important elements that define the quality of a good chatroom, and what could be improved?

Prompts:

Community activity?

Moderation?

Features?

(Examples of tangents)

In your opinion, what are the differences in the usage of the chatrooms by the open communities vs. the corporate teams?

Do you believe that the chatrooms (Slack or Gitter) drive project selection or vice versa? For example, could developers adopt certain projects because the community is already settled and active in Slack? or is it the opposite?

What are the elements to consider by a project team when selecting (or not) a chatroom as a central hub of communication?